

MEAN STRESS CORRECTION FOR CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites are widely used in different engineering applications for their high ratio of strength to weight. The fatigue behaviour of CFRP is sensitive to the mean stress even if under pure compressive loadings. The existing mean stress correction equations failed to account the mean stress effect for CFRP especially except Walker which, however, does not work under compressive loadings. A new mean stress correction equation was created to account for the mean stress effect for the CFRP composites under fatigue loadings which covers both tension and compression loadings.

Keywords: Fatigue, CFRP composite, Mean stress correction

INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites are widely used in different engineering applications for their high ratio of strength to weight. It is well known that fatigue behaviour of metals is significantly influenced by mean stress. Various equations have been established to account for the mean stress effect. Among these, Goodman [1], Gerber [2], Soderberg [3], Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) [4] and Walker [5] are the most commonly used. They are listed below:

$$\text{Goodman} \quad \frac{S_a}{S_{ao}} + \frac{S_m}{S_u} = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Gerber} \quad \frac{S_a}{S_{ao}} + \left(\frac{S_m}{S_u}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Soderberg} \quad \frac{S_a}{S_{ao}} + \frac{S_m}{S_y} = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{SWT} \quad S_{ao} = \sqrt{S_a(S_a + S_m)} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Walker} \quad S_{ao} = (S_a + S_m)^{1-\gamma} S_a^\gamma \quad (5)$$

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where S_a is the stress amplitude, S_m is the mean stress, S_{ao} is the equivalent stress amplitude at zero mean stress, S_u is the materials ultimate strength, S_y is the materials yield strength and γ is a material constant. SWT equation is a special case of Walker equation where $\gamma = 0.5$.

Mean stress was also reported to have a significant effect on fatigue behaviour of CFRP composites [6-21]. However, the mean stress correction on fatigue behaviour for these materials is less understood than metallic materials. In this research, a CFRP composite material with multiple fibre orientations manufactured by prepreg process was tested at a range of R values to assess the mean stress effect.

MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

A 2.4 mm thick of CFRP composite material was tested for its fatigue behaviour. The material consisted of 6 plies of 0.4 mm biaxial carbon fibre reinforcement (400gsm, 24K, STS40, ±45 NCF BIAx) and was manufactured by prepreg process. The lay-up of the material is [0/90/±45/0/90]_s. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and ultimate compression strength (UCS) of the material are 660 MPa and 430 MPa respectively. The ratio of UCS to UTS, χ_c is -0.65. The dimension of the fatigue specimen is 140x25x2.4 mm with 50 mm tabs on each side of the specimen, as shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 Dimension of fatigue specimen

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The test was carried out on a 50 KN DARTEC servo hydraulic test machine under constant load amplitude at 5 Hz in ambient and air with stress ratios, R, at 0.1, -1, -2 and $-\infty$ with applied nominal stress information summarized in Table 1. The schematic loading graph is demonstrated in Figure 2. Final fracture of the specimen was defined as fatigue life.

R	Stress Amplitude (MPa)	Maximum Stress (MPa)	Minimum Stress (MPa)	Mean Stress (MPa)
0.1	194~242	431~538	43~54	237~296
-1	150~231	150~231	-150~-231	0
-2	129~168	82~112	-165~-224	-41~-56
$-\infty$	90~133	0	-180~-266	-90~-133

TABLE 1 Fatigue test parameters

FIGURE 2 Loading schematic graph

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The fatigue test results are displayed in Figure 3. It is evident that mean stress does have a significant influence on the fatigue life.

FIGURE 3 Fatigue test results

Unlike metallic materials, the mean stress effect for this material showed completely different pattern: the more negative mean stress (compression), the worse fatigue performance. The assessment for the current existing mean stress correction equations is presented in Figures 4 to 7. It is evident that Goodman (as well as Soderberg), Gerber and Smith-Watson-Topper completely failed to account for the mean stress correction whereas Walker's with $\gamma=1.25$ can only account for the tensile-tension loading and the tension-compression loading when $\sigma_a > |\sigma_m|$ as displayed in Figure 7. In other word, Walker's equation failed to account for the data under purely compressive loadings.

FIGURE 4 Mean stress correction by Goodman equation

FIGURE 5 Mean stress correction by Gerber equation

FIGURE 6 Mean stress correction by SWT equation

FIGURE 7 Mean stress correction by Walker equation ($\gamma=1.25$)

A new mean stress correction equation (Equation 7) is created to account for the mean stress effect for the continuous CFRP composites:

$$S_{ao} = S_a \exp\left(\eta \frac{S_m}{S_a}\right) - S_m \quad (7)$$

where S_a is the stress amplitude, S_m is the mean stress, S_{ao} is the equivalent stress amplitude at zero mean stress and η is a material constant. The mean stress correction result is presented in Figure 8. It is evident that this equation works very well for all tension-tension, tension-compression and compression-compression loading regimes with $\eta=0.6$, as shown on Figure 9.

FIGURE 8 Result of mean stress correction by the new equation

FIGURE 9 Mean stress correction by the new equation

Based on the converted data, a master S-N curve at R=-1 can be created by merging all the data points together as presented in Figure 10. This increased the population of the data set for further statistical analysis.

FIGURE 10 Master S-N curve at R=-1 with various upper/lower bounds

The failure modes of the specimens at different test conditions were demonstrated in Figure 11. Two major modes were identified:

- Fibre breakage at tension-tension (T-T, R=0.1) loading.
- Local fiber/matrix delamination resulting local buckling at tension-compression (T-C, R=-1 and R=-2) and compression-compression (C-C, R=-∞) loadings.

This indicates that CFRP composite is much stronger under tension than under compression because the strong fibre took most of loads under tension, whereas the matrix, which is much weaker than the fibre, took most of loads under compression, therefore the fatigue behaviour of the composite is much weaker under tension/compression and compression/compression compared to that under tension/tension. This is also reflected by the monotonic behaviour of the material ($\chi=-0.65$). More attention must be taken for compressive load cases in engineering design/analysis for CFRP composites.

FIGURE 11 Failure modes

CONCLUSIONS

The existing mean stress correction equations failed to account for the CFRP composite data tested. A new mean stress correction equation was introduced to account for CFRP composites which covered all tension-tension, tension-compression and compression/compression loading modes.

The failure modes were fibre breakage under tension-tension and changed to local fiber/matrix delamination resulting local buckling under tension-compression or compression-compression.

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